

Investigation of Digital Game Addiction of Secondary School Students Regarding Personality Traits and Body Mass Index

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Deniz Mertkan GEZGİN

Trakya University, Faculty of Education, mertkan@trakya.edu.tr, 0000-0003-4688-043X, Edirne-Türkiye

Ecem ATABAY

Madalyon Psychiatry Clinic, ecem.atabay@madalyonklinik.com, 0000-0002-3009-8980, Istanbul-Türkiye

Abstract

The study aimed to examine the digital game addiction levels of secondary school students in terms of personality traits and body mass index (BMI). For this purpose, 251 secondary school students studying in Edirne province were reached. Data were obtained online and on a voluntary basis. In the study designed with the general survey method, the SPSS 23.0 statistical program was used for the analyses. Descriptive statistics and one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) were used in the analysis process. As a result of the findings, the level of digital game addiction among secondary school students corresponds to the low-risk group according to the categorized structure of the scale. In addition, within the scope of the categorized structure of the scale, secondary school students were divided into three groups: low-risk group, risky group, and addicted group in terms of digital game addiction. When the BMI values of these three groups were analysed, it was seen that there was no significant difference. However, significant differences were found between the groups in terms of personality traits. According to the findings, it was seen that the extraversion and agreeableness scores of the students in the digital game addicted group were lower than the other groups, while in terms of neuroticism personality type, the digital game addict group had higher digital game addiction scores than the other groups. As a result of the study, it can be said that personality traits differ in terms of digital game addiction. In addition, it can be said that BMI does not make a difference in digital game addiction groups.

Keywords: Addiction, Digital Games, BMI, Dijital technologies

Introduction

Digital games can be defined as interactive entertainment tools that reach large masses through computers, consoles, mobile devices and other platforms with the development of technology. These games attract users with the virtual worlds and social interaction opportunities they offer and have become a part of the daily lives of people of all ages around the world. Digital games, which are widely preferred especially among the young population, are not only fun but also support skills such as strategy development, problem solving and cooperation. However, the increasing popularity of these games may cause some individuals to develop uncontrolled gaming habits. The widespread use of digital games leads to an increasing addiction trend, especially among the young population (Gezgin, 2023). Digital game addiction is a condition in which individuals spend excessive time and energy on digital games; this behaviour cannot be controlled; ongoing game-playing behaviour is continued despite the harmful consequences; and psychological withdrawal symptoms are observed (Griffiths, 2005). This type of addiction can cause the person to have difficulty fulfilling daily responsibilities, experience withdrawal symptoms when they stop playing games, and lose interest in activities other than games (World Health Organization, 2019; American Psychiatric Association, 2013). Secondary school students stand out as a group at risk for digital game addiction because they are at the beginning of adolescence and interact intensively with technology (Namlı & Demir, 2020). This addiction not only has negative effects on

social and academic life but also has serious consequences for students' physical health (Strasburger et al., 2010; Mustafaoğlu & Yasacı, 2018). In particular, long-term gaming habits that encourage sedentary lifestyles can lead to an increase in body mass index (BMI), which can increase the risk of obesity and other health problems (Yılmaz & Gezgin, 2023). In a study of 405 adolescents, they found that digital game addiction had a negative relationship with physical activity level and physical activity level had a negative relationship with BMI (Gülü et al., 2023). In another study conducted with adolescents, a negative relationship between internet addiction and BMI was reported (Canan et al., 2014). Considering that increases in overweight and obesity have become an important public health problem worldwide (Wyatt et al., 2006; Abarca-Gómez et al., 2017), it is necessary to investigate the structure between digital game addiction and BMI. Investigating the physical health to be gained or lost from childhood in secondary school students, who are more prone to digital games, shows the importance of the study.

Personal traits were also examined as an additional variable in the research. This is because personality traits play a critical role in determining individuals' tendencies towards digital game addiction (Mehroof & Griffiths, 2010). Widely accepted theoretical frameworks such as the Five Factor Personality Model provide valuable clues in understanding individuals' gaming habits and the possibility of these habits turning into addiction. For example, research on how personality traits such as extraversion, agreeableness, conscientiousness, neuroticism, and openness to experience shape individuals' game-playing behaviours reveals important information in this field (Basha, 2021; Gervasi et al., 2017; Kağızmanlı, 2019; Kim et al., 2008; Kircaburun et al., 2018; Mehroof & Griffiths, 2010; Ünal, 2024). For instance, in a study conducted by Ünal (2024), significant positive relationships were found between openness to experience and game addiction, and negative relationships were found between neuroticism and game addiction. In his thesis study, Kağızmanlı (2019) revealed that extraversion and openness to experience were not related to game addiction, while neuroticism was positively related, and agreeableness and conscientiousness were negatively related. In another study, the results obtained with the Five Factor Model personal traits revealed that neuroticism was positively correlated with pathological game playing, while extraversion, openness to experience, agreeableness, and conscientiousness were negatively correlated with pathological game playing (Reyes et al., 2019). As can be seen, studies in the relevant literature reveal different results. In this respect, it is important to investigate the relationship between personality traits and game addiction with participant groups of different cultures and levels. For this reason, this study examines the prevalence of game addiction in terms of personality traits and BMI. In this context, answers to the following research questions were sought:

1. What is the level of digital game addiction among middle school students?
2. Is there a significant difference in the level of digital game addiction among middle school students regarding personal traits and BMI?

Method

In this study, in which the levels of digital game addiction among middle school students were examined regarding personal traits and BMI variables, the general survey method was used. Survey studies are studies that aim to describe the characteristics of the views of large masses (Büyüköztürk et al., 2016).

Participants

The participants of the study were 251 secondary school students studying in educational institutions affiliated to the Ministry of National Education in Edirne province in Turkey. 135 of the participants are girls (53.8%) and 116 of them are boys (46.2%). 90 of the students are 5th grade (35.9%), 79 are 6th grade (31.5%), 36 are 7th grade (14.4%) and 46 are 8th grade (18.2%) students. Whole students play digital games. In addition, the types of games played by students are war, sports, action-

adventure, survival and racing games in order of intensity. BMI was found to be 18.53 (BMI values between 11.45 and 30.34) on average in the study. In conclusion, adolescents generally fall into the normal weight range; however, age- and sex-specific growth curve analysis is required for a thorough evaluation. However, in this study, it was assumed that the participant group was of normal weight.

Data Collection Tools

A research form was developed by the researchers to collect data for the study. This form consists of two parts. The first part includes the demographic information of the participant and consists of questions about gender, grade level, type of game played, height and weight. In the second part, the “*Digital Game Addiction Scale for Children*” and “*Big Five Personality Traits Scale*” were used.

Digital Game Addiction Scale in Children. The measurement tool developed by Hazar and Hazar (2017) consists of 24 questions. A 5-point Likert scale was used to evaluate the statements in the scale (1 = Strongly Disagree, ..., 5 = Strongly Agree). The lowest score that can be obtained from the scale is “24” and the highest score is “120”. In the scoring of the scale; 1-24: Normal group, 25-48: Low risk group, 49-72: Risky group, 73-96: Addicted group, 97- 120: Highly addicted group”. Cronbach Alpha internal consistency coefficient for the scale was determined as .90. The Cronbach Alpha internal consistency coefficient for this study was found to be .91.

Big Five Personality Traits Scale. 10-item Big Five Personality Traits Scale developed by Rammstedt and John (2007) was adapted to Turkish by Horzum et al. (2017). The scale comprises five sub-dimensions: extraversion, agreeableness, conscientiousness, neuroticism, and openness to experience, and there are a total of two items for each dimension, one of which is reverse. To put it briefly, agreeableness is the quality of being dependable, polite, and giving; conscientiousness is the quality of being careful, organized, hardworking, trustworthy, and on time; extraversion is the quality of being talkative, energetic, gregarious, and passionate; neuroticism is the quality of being erratic, short-tempered, and whiny; and openness to experience is the quality of being creative, inquisitive, original, and possessing a wide range of interests. These two items are combined to form the sub-dimension score. It was revealed that Cronbach's alpha internal consistency values for the sub-dimensions of the scale ranged between 0.81 and 0.90, and the composite reliability coefficients ranged between 0.73 and 0.85. Scale assessment was performed according to the sub-dimensions. As the scores for each sub-dimension increase, the characteristics of that dimension increase in the individual (Horzum et al., 2017).

Data Collection and Analysis

Firstly, an ethics committee report was obtained for the study (Decision No. 04/23 taken at the meeting of the Trakya University Social and Human Sciences Research Ethics Committee on April 24, 2024). After ethics committee permission was obtained, data was collected online via Google Surveys in April and May. During the data collection process, students and parents were first informed about the study. They were provided with detailed information about the purpose of the research, the procedures involved, and the potential risks and benefits. It was explained that participation was completely voluntary, and that they had the right to withdraw from the study at any point without any consequences. Additionally, it was assured that the data would be used only for scientific purposes and kept confidential. Written informed consent was obtained from both students and their parents prior to participation. In the data analysis process, descriptive statistics (frequency, percentage, mean, and standard deviation) and one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) from parametric tests were used. The SPSS 23.0 package program was used for data analysis. Before starting the analysis, Kolmogorov-Smirnov and Shapiro-Wilk tests were applied to determine whether the data were normally distributed. However, after the outliers were removed, it was observed that the data were not normally distributed ($p < .05$). Therefore, skewness and kurtosis values were calculated (skewness = .407; kurtosis = .141). When the data were analysed, it was seen that these values were between -1.50 and +1.50, and it was accepted that the data were normally distributed (Tabachnick & Fidell, 2013). The following formula was used to calculate the body mass index in the study ($BMI = \text{weight} / (\text{height} * \text{height})$ in meter).

Findings

In the study, the average score of digital game addiction of secondary school students was found to be 54.28. According to the cross-sectional structure in the scale used, it was determined that the students were in the low-risk group. Table 1 shows the score values obtained from the scale.

Table 1. Descriptive Statistics of Digital Game Addiction Scores

Variable	N	Min.	Max.	Mean	Std. Dev.	Skewness	Kurtosis
Digital Game Addiction	251	26.00	96.00	54.28	18.516	.407	.141

In addition, students were categorically divided into three groups. Respectively, 109 of the students were in the low-risk group, the 94 of the students were in the risky group and the 48 of the students were in the dependent group. Table 2 shows this grouping.

Table 2. Categorization of Students Based on Digital Game Addiction Levels

Variable	Groups	N	%
Digital Game Addiction	Low Risky Group (1)	109	43.4
	Risky Group (2)	94	37.5
	Addicted Group (3)	48	19.1
	Total	251	100.0

In the study, ANOVA test was applied to measure whether there was a difference between the game addiction groups in terms of personality traits and BMI. As a result of the analyses, there were differences between the groups in extraversion, agreeableness and neuroticism personality types. The TUKEY test, one of the post hoc tests, was used to determine which groups the difference was between. According to the findings, the extraversion score of the students in the addicted group(M=3.09) was significantly lower than the risky(M=3.80) and low-risk groups(M=3.83). In terms of agreeableness, the score of the students in the dependent group(M=3.11) was significantly lower than the low-risk group (3.82). Finally, in terms of neuroticism, the scores of the students in the addicted group(M=3.60) were significantly higher than the low-risk (M=2.81) and high-risk groups(M=2.89). Another variable in the study was given as BMI. The results of the analysis in terms of BMI showed that there was no significant difference between the groups($p > .05$). All the ANOVA results are shown in Table 3.

Table 3. ANOVA Results Comparing Personality Traits and BMI Across Digital Game Addiction Groups

Variables		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	p	Difference
Extraversion	Between Groups	16.604	2	8.302	5.582	.00*	3<1, 3<2
	Within Groups	368.830	248	1.487			
	Total	385.434	250				
Agreeableness	Between Groups	7.639	2	3.819	5.431	.00*	3<1
	Within Groups	174.415	248	.703			
	Total	182.054	250				
Conscientiousness	Between Groups	5.150	2	2.575	2.417	.09	-
	Within Groups	264.171	248	1.065			
	Total	269.321	250				
Neuroticism	Between Groups	10.515	2	5.257	5.307	.00*	3>1, 3>2
	Within Groups	245.685	248	.991			
	Total	256.199	250				
Openness to experience	Between Groups	4.089	2	2.044	2.493	.09	-
	Within Groups	203.324	248	.820			
	Total	207.412	250				
BMI	Between Groups	20.577	2	10.288	.857	.43	-
	Within Groups	2976.204	248	12.001			
	Total	2996.781	250				

*1: Low Risky Group, 2: Risky Group, 3: Addicted Group.

Discussion and Conclusions

The aim of this study is to examine the digital game addiction levels of secondary school students in terms of personality traits and BMI. There are two main research questions in the study. In the analyses made in response to the first of these questions, 'What are the digital game addiction levels of secondary school students?', it was determined that the students were in the low-risk group in terms of all of them. In support of the findings of the study, there are studies reporting that adolescents have a low risk of digital game addiction (Başdaş & Özbey, 2020; Karaca et al., 2016; Savcı & Aysan, 2017; Parılı & Gezgin, 2024; Taş & Güneş, 2019; Subu et al, 2021). However, when the level of digital game addiction was analysed categorically, it was seen that there were three groups: the low-risk group (43.4%), the risky group (37.5%), and the addicted group (19.1%). However, in terms of frequency and percentage, it was determined that the density was in the low-risk group and the risky group. In the context of these results, it can be said that secondary school students, the participants of the study, are at risk for digital game addiction. When the related literature was examined in terms of digital game addiction, some studies were found. For example, in a study conducted by Dursun and Çapan (2018) with adolescents in Turkey, it was stated that adolescents were at risk for digital game addiction. In another study conducted by Yiğit and Günüç (2020) on children's digital game addiction, it was found that 15.1% of children were addicted and 44% were at risk of addiction. As can be seen, adolescents are at risk for digital game addiction, and it is thought that this addiction will increase with the development of technology. The reason for this can be attributed to the increase in digital games in addition to psychosocial needs and the development of addictive mechanisms over time, depending on technology.

When the findings were analyzed in terms of BMI, another variable examined in the study, no significant difference was observed between the low-risk group, the high-risk group, and the addicted group. Based on these findings, it can be concluded that BMI does not significantly differentiate digital game addiction groups. Several studies in the relevant literature support these findings. For instance, Polat and Topal (2022) and Saquib et al. (2017) found that BMI was not a significant determinant of digital game addiction in adolescents. However, some studies suggest that adolescents who spend more time playing digital games may have higher BMI values due to prolonged sitting and decreased physical activity. For example, Başdaş and Özbey (2020) discovered that obese adolescents had higher average scores of digital game addiction, and a low positive correlation was found between BMI and digital game addiction scores according to age. Similarly, Shen et al. (2021) reported that adolescents who spend extended periods online and are engaged in video games tend to have higher BMI scores, which is associated with being overweight. Another a study conducted with young adolescents in India found a negative but weak relationship between digital game addiction levels and BMI (Subu et al., 2021). This suggests that the literature presents varying results regarding the relationship between BMI and digital game addiction, including findings that both align with and differ from the results of this study. Moreover, the literature suggests that digital games may predispose adolescents to irregular eating habits and sedentary lifestyles, which have been associated with both obesity (Saunders et al., 2021) and weight loss (Simons et al., 2014). Considering these different results, more investigation is required to fully comprehend the connection between BMI and digital game addiction.

At the end of the study, digital game addiction groups were analyzed in terms of personality traits. The findings revealed that the extraversion level of secondary school students in the addicted group was significantly lower than in the other groups, while the neuroticism level in the addicted group was significantly higher. Additionally, the agreeableness level of participants in the addicted group was significantly lower than that of those in the low-risk group. When the related literature is examined, it is seen that there are many studies between personality traits and addictions. This shows that personality traits play a role in addiction. Especially the findings related to neurotic personality type stand out. In a study that partially supports the findings of the study in this context, it was found that game addiction in children was positively correlated with neurotic personality traits, but there was no significant relationship with personality traits such as extraversion, self-control and openness to experience (Basha,

2021). Similarly, extroverted and agreeable students had lower levels of game addiction, according to a study that partially corroborated the study's findings. However, openness to experience and conscientiousness did not correlate with game addiction (Vollmer et al., 2014). In a study showing a significant difference in personality traits for addictive behaviours related to different online activities, it was also reported that less conscientiousness and low openness were significantly associated with gaming addiction (Wang et al., 2015). In contrast, one study suggests that students with low conscientiousness are more likely to be interested in games that can fulfil their needs easily and quickly, especially those that can give them a sense of achievement without great effort (Kim et al., 2022). However, in our study, no difference was found between the groups in terms of conscientiousness. As can be seen from the findings, the studies in the literature differ. When the findings of our study and the findings of other studies are considered, it is suggested that digital game addiction is not only caused by certain personality traits of individuals but also that these traits may interact with game playing motivations, game playing time, and game type. For instance, while some individuals play games with specific motivations, such as coping with stress or seeking social interaction, these motivations, combined with certain personality traits, may increase the risk of addiction. This suggests that prevention and intervention strategies for digital game addiction should consider not only personality traits but also the interaction of these traits with motivations.

In line with the findings from this study, it was determined that secondary school students are at risk for digital game addiction. As a result of these findings, it is recommended that schools, in particular, collaborate with psychologists to create workshops that aim to increase resilience among students with neurotic personality traits. Because these students are at higher risk for digital game addiction. Parents should also be encouraged to monitor their children's gaming habits and support alternative activities that reduce sedentary behaviour and encourage social interaction. Finally, policymakers could consider developing community programs that integrate physical activities with gaming to reduce sedentary habits associated with digital games. This could further reduce physical and psychological health-related risks among adolescents. In addition, there are some limitations that should be mentioned in the study. One limitation of the study is that data was collected through self-reported questionnaires, which may introduce bias and limit the accuracy of the results. To address this limitation, future research should consider utilising longitudinal study designs that include direct data collection from the gaming platforms or devices used by participants. Such approaches would enable more precise measurement of playing time and its correlation with addiction, thereby yielding more robust and reliable findings. Additionally, the study found that BMI did not differ significantly among digital game addiction groups, which was an unexpected result. This finding contrasts with existing literature that suggests a relationship between BMI, obesity, and digital game addiction. Thus, it is important to conduct further studies with different participant groups to explore this relationship more thoroughly. Finally, the study observed that personality traits differ across game addiction groups, a finding that is supported by existing literature. This suggests that identifying personality types in adolescents could be an important issue for developing preventive measures against digital game addiction.

References

- Abarca-Gómez, L., Abdeen, Z. A., Hamid, Z. A., Abu-Rmeileh, N. M., Acosta-Cazares, B., Acuin, C., ... & Cho, Y. (2017). Worldwide trends in body-mass index, underweight, overweight, and obesity from 1975 to 2016: a pooled analysis of 2416 population-based measurement studies in 128·9 million children, adolescents, and adults. *The lancet*, 390(10113), 2627-2642.
- American Psychiatric Association. (2013). *Diagnostic and Statistical Manual of Mental Disorders (5th ed.) (DSM-5)*. Arlington, VA: American Psychiatric Publishing.
- Başdaş, Ö., & Özbey, H. (2020). Digital game addiction, obesity, and social anxiety among adolescents. *Archives of Psychiatric Nursing*, 34(2), 17-20.
- Basha, E. (2021). The relationship between game addiction and personality traits. *Erciyes Journal of Education*, 5(2), 149-160.

- Büyüköztürk, Ş., Kılıç, Ç. E., Akgün, Ö. E., Karadeniz, Ş., & Demirel, F. (2016). *Scientific research methods*. Ankara: Pegem Akademi.
- Canan, F., Yildirim, O., Ustunel, T. Y., Sinani, G., Kaleli, A. H., Gunes, C., & Ataoglu, A. (2014). The relationship between internet addiction and body mass index in Turkish adolescents. *Cyberpsychology, Behavior, and Social Networking*, 17(1), 40-45.
- Dursun, A., & Çapan, B. E. (2018). Ergenlerde dijital oyun bağımlılığı ve psikolojik ihtiyaçlar. *İnönü Üniversitesi Eğitim Fakültesi Dergisi*, 19(2), 128-140.
- Gervasi, A. M., La Marca, L., Costanzo, A., Pace, U., Guglielmucci, F. & Schimmenti, A. (2017). Personality and internet gaming disorder: A systematic review of recent literature. *Current Addiction Reports*, 4, 293-307.
- Gezgin, D. M. (2023). *Çocuklarda Problemlili Teknoloji Kullanımı, Olumsuz Etkileri ve Çözüm Önerileri*. Paradigma Akademi (1. Baskı), Çanakkale-Türkiye.
- Griffiths, M. D. (2005). A 'components' model of addiction within a biopsychosocial framework. *Journal of Substance Use*, 10(4), 191-197.
- Gülü, M., Yagin, F. H., Gocer, I., Yapici, H., Ayyildiz, E., Clemente, F. M., ... & Nobari, H. (2023). Exploring obesity, physical activity, and digital game addiction levels among adolescents: A study on machine learning-based prediction of digital game addiction. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 14, 1097145.
- Hazar, Z. & Hazar, M. (2017). Çocuklar için dijital oyun bağımlılığı ölçeği. *Journal of Human Sciences*, 14(1), 203-216.
- Horzum, M., Ayas, T., & Padır, M. (2017). Beş Faktör Kişilik Ölçeğinin Türk Kültürüne Uyarlanması. *Sakarya University Journal of Education*, 7(2), 398-408.
- Kağızmanlı, N. (2019). *Ergenlerde beş faktör kişilik özelliklerinin dijital oyun bağımlılık düzeyleri üzerindeki yordayıcı etkisinin incelenmesi* (Yayımlanmamış Yüksek Lisans Tezi. Bayburt Üniversitesi/Sosyal Bilimler Enstitüsü, Bayburt.
- Karaca, S., Gok, C., Kalay, E., Basbug, M., Hekim, M., Onan, N., & Barlas, G. (2016). Investigating the association between computer game addiction and social anxiety in secondary school students. *Clinical and Experimental Health Sciences*, 6(1).
- Kim, D., Nam, J. K., & Keum, C. (2022). Adolescent Internet gaming addiction and personality characteristics by game genre. *Plos one*, 17(2), e0263645.
- Kim, E. J., Namkoong, K., Ku, T., & Kim, S. J. (2008). The relationship between online game addiction and aggression, self-control and narcissistic personality traits. *European psychiatry*, 23(3), 212-218.
- Kircaburun, K., Jonason, P. K. & Griffiths, M. D. (2018). The dark tetrad traits and problematic online gaming: The mediating role of online gaming motives and moderating role of game types. *Pers Individ Dif*, 135, 298-303.
- Mehroof, M., & Griffiths, M. D. (2010). Online gaming addiction: The role of sensation seeking, self-control, neuroticism, aggression, state anxiety, and trait anxiety. *Cyberpsychology, behavior, and social networking*, 13(3), 313-316.
- Mustafaoğlu, R., & Yasacı, Z. (2018). Dijital oyun oynamanın çocukların ruhsal ve fiziksel sağlığı üzerine olumsuz etkileri. *Bağımlılık Dergisi*, 19(3), 51-58.
- Namlı, S., & Demir, G. T. (2020). The Relationship between Attitudes towards Digital Gaming and Sports. *Turkish Online Journal of Educational Technology-TOJET*, 19(1), 40-52.

- Parıltı, C., & Gezgin, D. M. (2024). *Psychosocial Effects of Digital Game Addiction in Secondary School Students: A Study on Demographic Factors, Academic Achievement and Social Support Status*. Ege 11th International Conference on Social Sciences, June 1 – 3, 2024- Izmir-Türkiye.
- Polat, A., & Topal, M. (2022). Relationship between digital game addiction with body mass index, academic achievement, player types, gaming time: A cross-sectional study. *Journal of Educational Technology and Online Learning*, 5(4), 901-915.
- Rammstedt, B., & John, O. P. (2007). Measuring Personality in One Minute or Less: A 10Item Short Version of the Big Five Inventory in English and German. *Journal of Research in Personality*, 41, 203–212.
- Reyes, M. E. S., Davis, R. D., Lim, R. A. N. N., Lim, K. R. S., Paulino, R. F., Carandang, A. M. D., & Azarraga, M. G. S. (2019). Five-factor model traits as predictors of pathological gaming among selected Filipino gamers. *Psychological Studies*, 64, 213-220.
- Saquib, N., Saquib, J., Wahid, A., Ahmed, A. A., Dhuhayr, H. E., Zaghoul, M. S., ... Al-Mazrou, A. (2017). Video game addiction and psychological distress among expatriate adolescents in Saudi Arabia. *Addictive Behaviors Reports*, 6, 112–117.
- Savcı, M., & Aysan, F. (2017). Teknolojik bağımlılıklar ve sosyal bağıllık: İnternet bağımlılığı, sosyal medya bağımlılığı, dijital oyun bağımlılığı ve akıllı telefon bağımlılığının sosyal bağıllığı yordayıcı etkisi. *Dusunen Adam*, 30(3), 202-216.
- Shen, C., Dumontheil, I., Thomas, M., Rössli, M., Elliott, P., & Toledano, M. (2021). Digital technology use and BMI: Evidence from a cross-sectional analysis of an adolescent cohort study. *Journal of Medical Internet Research*, 23(7), e26485.
- Simons, M., Chinapaw, M. J., van de Bovenkamp, M., de Boer, M. R., Seidell, J. C., Brug, J., & de Vet, E. (2014). Active video games as a tool to prevent excessive weight gain in adolescents: rationale, design and methods of a randomized controlled trial. *BMC public health*, 14, 275.
- Strasburger, V. C., Jordan, A. B., & Donnerstein, E. (2010). Health effects of media on children and adolescents. *Pediatrics*, 125(4), 756-767.
- Subu, M. A., Al-Yateem, N., Waluyo, I., Dias, J. M., Rahman, S. A., Agustino, R., ... & Al Marzooqi, A. (2021, July). Relationship between Internet gaming addiction and body mass index status among Indonesian junior high school students. In *2021 IEEE 45th Annual Computers, Software, and Applications Conference (COMPSAC)* (pp. 1391-1393). IEEE.
- Tabachnick, B. G. & Fidell, L. S. (2013). *Using multivariate statistics (Sixth Edition)*. USA: Pearson Education Limited.
- Taş, İ., & Güneş, Z. (2019). 8-12 yaş arası çocuklarda bilgisayar oyun bağımlılığı, aleksitimi, sosyal anksiyete, yaş ve cinsiyetin incelenmesi. *Klinik Psikiyatri*, 22(1), 83-92.
- Ünal, F. (2024). *Geç ergenlik döneminde kişilik özellikleri ve oyun bağımlılığı arasındaki ilişkide baş etme yöntemleri ve algılanan sosyal desteğin düzenleyici rolünün incelenmesi*. Klinik Psikoloji, Lisansüstü Eğitim Enstitüsü, Işık Üniversitesi.
- Wang, C. W., Ho, R. T., Chan, C. L., & Tse, S. (2015). Exploring personality characteristics of Chinese adolescents with internet-related addictive behaviors: Trait differences for gaming addiction and social networking addiction. *Addictive behaviors*, 42, 32-35.
- World Health Organization. (2019). International Classification of Diseases (ICD-11): Gaming Disorder. <https://www.who.int/features/qa/gaming-disorder/en/> adresinden 13.08.2024 tarihinde erişilmiştir.

- Wyatt, S. B., Winters, K. P., & Dubbert, P. M. (2006). Overweight and obesity: prevalence, consequences, and causes of a growing public health problem. *The American journal of the medical sciences*, 331(4), 166-174.
- Vollmer, C., Randler, C., Horzum, M. B., & Ayas, T. (2014). Computer game addiction in adolescents and its relationship to chronotype and personality. *Sage Open*, 4(1), 2158244013518054.
- Yılmaz, B. E., & Gezgin, D. M. (2023). Overuse of technology and obesity: could technology addiction be one of the causes of obesity? International Aegean Conferences on Social Sciences & Humanities-VII, April 26-27, İzmir-Türkiye.
- Yiğit, E., & Günüç, S. (2020). Çocukların Dijital Oyun Bağımlılığına Göre Aile Profillerinin Belirlenmesi. *Van Yüzüncü Yıl Üniversitesi Eğitim Fakültesi Dergisi*, 17(1), 144-174.